

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

(l)

(m)

(n)

(o)

(p)

(q)

(r)

Supplementary Figure S1. Differences between boys and girls in all parameters, (a)-(d) anthropometrics, (e) – (j) physical fitness tests, (k) concentration score, (l) – (r) health-related Quality of Life (HRQOL) sub-scales